

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 4, No. 6; June 28, 1998

Dear Readers:

This issue of J.UCS is again a good example of the wide coverage of the journal: from quite theoretical to rather applied research, the four papers present a broad selection of interesting topics. I hope you will enjoy reading them.

As much as I wish you all a good summer (ahem, winter down under), I would like to urge you not to forget submitting high quality papers to J.UCS and to also encourage your colleagues to do so.

Yours cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
email: hmaurer@iicm.edu